

QUESTIONS OF DISTINGUISHING EXTORTION FROM OTHER CRIMES

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Annotation: In legal practice, many disputed moments arise regarding the distinction between extortion and related offenses. According to the author, this arises from the insufficient explanations regarding the differentiation of these criminal offenses. This paper examines the features allowing to distinguish adjacent criminal offenses from the offense of extortion.

Keywords: extortion, banditry, robbery, qualification.

The correct distinction between related criminal offenses has significant theoretical and practical importance. It ensures precise qualification and, consequently, fair punishment. The issue of distinguishing crimes belongs to the most complex and, at the same time, insufficiently developed areas of criminal law theory. Errors that may be made by law enforcement officials in applying criminal law norms are related to incorrect qualification of crimes. Difficulties in this context are mainly due to the fact that this crime has common features with other related criminal offenses. For accurate qualification of the crime, it is necessary to clearly define the boundaries between it and related offenses. By identifying characteristic features inherent in this offense and absent in other cases, gradually delving into the analysis of both legal norms and factual circumstances, we arrive at a set of features that characterize this crime and distinguish it from others.

Since extortion shares many similarities with banditry and robbery, this situation becomes the most significant problem in the field of criminal law. All these crimes are committed by the use of violence or threat of violence, which increases their degree of social danger. The legislator has defined the level of violence both in the case of violent robbery and in the case of banditry. In the context of violence in extortion, the form of this violence was not specified, indicating the inclusion of characteristics of both non-dangerous and dangerous violence.

The distinction between extortion, banditry and robbery is determined by the similarity of their external manifestations and their impact on property rights, as well as the threat to the life and health of the victim. In criminal law

theory, most researchers support the view that the main difference between these crimes lies in intent. In the case of extortion, violence and seizure of property will occur in the future. The intent to use violence or transfer property in extortion is directed towards the future. If violence and obtaining property coincide in time, the act is classified as robbery (according to Article 166 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) or banditry (according to Article 164 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

When distinguishing extortion from banditry and robbery, it is important to consider that in the case of extortion, the threat of violence is directed towards obtaining property in the future, not at the moment the threat is made. If the threat has been carried out, the committed act will be classified according to the article of the Criminal Code on extortion, and also, if there are grounds, under the article providing for responsibility for actions committed during the implementation of the threat[1].

In extortion, violence can manifest through threats of violence against the victim or their relatives, damage or destruction of property, as well as through destruction, alteration, seizure, or blocking of the victim's information resources, disclosure of confidential information, or dissemination of information defaming the victim (Part 1 of Article 165 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). In banditry, violence takes the form of physical violence and threats of physical violence.

However, there are cases where both extortion and banditry may involve a combination of crimes: a person, using violence that poses a danger to life and health, demands property in the future, but some of it is stolen before or after the violence is applied. In cases where violence in banditry and robbery serves as a means of obtaining or retaining property, when committing extortion accompanied by threats, it is necessary to clearly distinguish banditry and robbery from extortion involving violence.

In committing extortion, the intent of the person is directed towards obtaining financial gain in the future, while in banditry and robbery, the acquisition of property occurs simultaneously with violent actions or immediately after them. In banditry, the object of the crime is property, whereas in extortion, it can be not only the property itself but also the right to it (for example, a contract, receipt, or other document confirming a debt to the extortionist, or a document through which certain property rights transfer to the extortionist), financial benefits, or actions of a financial nature (such as performing work, providing a service, etc.). Therefore, the problem of

distinguishing these offenses arises only when the object of the crime is property.

Another important distinguishing feature between extortion and banditry is that in extortion, the act is committed exclusively using psychological violence, expressed through threats, whereas in robbery, both psychological and physical violence can be used. In the case of extortion, threats have a broader nature (including threats of violence against the victim or their relatives, damage or destruction of property, as well as destruction, alteration, seizure, or blocking of the victim's information resources, disclosure of confidential information about them), which are aimed at intimidating the victim, while in banditry, violence is used as a means of acquiring property.

In the case of extortion, demands not supported by threats do not constitute a crime. If there is a demand for the transfer of someone else's property, rights to it, or the performance of other property-related actions, but there is no threat or it takes a different form than specified in Article 165 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, then the elements of extortion are not fulfilled. It is important to note that the subjective perception of the nature and intensity of the threat by the victim does not affect the qualification of the crime.

The demand in extortion is aimed at violating fundamental objects (property relations), while the threat is directed at additional objects (personal goods). Therefore, for extortion, both actions described in the law are mandatory, and the crime is considered completed at the moment of making a demand backed by a threat.

The purpose of using physical violence in extortion is to demonstrate to the victim that serious consequences await them in case of refusal to transfer property or perform other property-related actions, thereby increasing the likelihood of satisfying the criminal demands. Therefore, violence serves as a means of coercion to desired behavior, reinforcing the demands.

During extortion, a person can use any form of violence, including both life-threatening and non-life-threatening violence, whereas in banditry, violence is always considered life-threatening. Extortion is considered a completed crime at the moment when demands are made by the individual for the transfer of property, rights to it, or the performance of other property-related actions, while robbery is considered completed from the moment of the attack.

N.A. Lopashenko highlights the following features:

a) Robbery involves theft with the use of violence or threats;

b) Banditry and extortion are truncated forms. Robbery includes an attack with dangerous violence or threat thereof, while extortion involves a demand with a threat;

c) Differences in types of threats: for robbery and theft, the level of danger is defined, while for extortion, the threat can be any form of violence;

d) Differences in the time of obtaining property: in robbery and theft, it is immediate, while in extortion, it is after some time;

e) Differences in the time of threat realization: in robbery and theft, it can be carried out immediately, while in extortion, it can be done after some time. Violence in extortion is possible, but it only reinforces the threat rather than nullifying it. [2].

Thus, extortion, despite its proximity to banditry and robbery and the challenges in distinguishing it in practice, has a number of distinguishing features that allow it to be differentiated from other criminal offenses based on both objective and subjective characteristics.

References:

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